

Deliverable 3.4 – WP3. HIKR Multi Actor Approach

EURAKNOS

***Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European
Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System***

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TASK Number 3.4

HIKR multi-actor approach

Summary

Task description: Report on HIKR multi actor approach

Results and conclusions: Ensuring end-user representation in the **MA consortium** and a good structure and management of the MA partnership within all WPs and tasks is crucial for an efficient implementation of collaborative processes. Moreover, a co-construction shared by all actors involved in the project on ‘how to work together’ contributes to construction of a trust-based ecosystem of actors and is likely to increase the mutual understanding between actors. A 2-day workshop was held in Paris on 12th and 13th December 2019 with end-users and TN practitioners to identify recommendations on how to foster and enhance end user-engagement in all phases of a projects’ life span, from conceptualisation, to implementation, (initiation and execution) to post-execution.

Apart from end-user representation in the MA consortium, meanstreaming end-user engagement in all steps of project execution is essential to increase the impact of the MAA. In this report recommendations are provided to foster the approach in all project activities.

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1.3 List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

EC	European Commission
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership
e-KRP	e-Knowledge Reservoir Platform
FG	Focus Groups
Actor WG	Actor Working Group
HIKR	High Impact Knowledge Reservoir
IA	Innovation Actions
KIP	Knowledge Innovation Panel
KR	Knowledge Reservoir
OGs	Operational Groups
RDP	Rural Development Program
RIA	Research Innovation Actions
RN	Rural Network
SIB	Strategic Innovation Board
TNs	Thematic Networks
WG	Working Group
M&E	Monitoring and Evaluation
KTN	Knowledge Transfer Network
MA	MA
MAA	MAapproach
P2P	Peer to peer
KE	Knowledge Exchange
CSA	Community Supported Agriculture
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators

2 Introduction

Europe's future economic growth and jobs will increasingly have to come from innovation in products, services and business models (European Commission, 2014). The traditional, top-down linear model of knowledge 'transfer' from science to farmers is increasingly outdated: knowledge no longer only flows in one direction. Challenges in agriculture and forestry are becoming more and more complex, so it is necessary to see them from all angles (EIP AGRI, 2017). In this context, agricultural professionals increasingly realize that adopting a strategic multi-actor approach (MAA) will maximize the impact of their work.

Multi-actor (MA) projects bring together partners with complementary types of knowledge – scientific, practical and other (such as farmers, researchers, advisers and agri-businesses) in order to tackle real needs from the field, supporting the idea that innovation is strengthened by combining knowledge and experiences from a diverse range of people (EIP AGRI, 2017). The MAA puts into practice the “interactive innovation model” which is promoted by EIP-AGRI. This involves focusing on different dimensions simultaneously, including technical, organisational and social aspects, which helps to bridge the gap between science and practice, applying a “systems approach”.

The interactive innovation model is also used by Thematic Networks (TNs) who work on collecting existing knowledge and best practices on a given theme to make it available in easily understandable and engaging formats for end-users, such as farmers, foresters, advisers and others. The EURAKNOS project aims to reinforce the EU agricultural knowledge base through the development of a blueprint for a data system that enables the farming/rural community easier access to best practices from all EU H2020 TNs. To realize this, the EURAKNOS project connects all TNs to 1.) map the stored knowledge within each network 2) develop a standardised approach to store knowledge and 3.) design a common data system to make this knowledge more accessible, findable, interoperable and reusable for the agricultural innovation community in Europe.

EURAKNOS brings together a project consortium of 17 different actors including academia, advisory centres, government institutions, SME, NGO and farmer organisations from 11 EU countries from different regions across Europe. Some partners are involved in the European Rural Development Network and others are involved in other relevant H2020 proposals or have strong links with relevant European (e.g. EUFFRAS, member of SCAR SWG-AKIS group) and international organisations (e.g. FAO, OECD, the European Agroforestry). The main outcome of EURAKNOS is to have all the information from across these innovation networks more accessible to farming and rural communities by having it collated in and promoted through one system.

There is no doubt about the significant added-value of adopting a MAA for communication, dissemination and exploitation purposes. It is foreseeable that this approach contributes significantly to enlarge the spectrum of knowledge and information available in project consortia. However the implementation of such a complex interactive MAA, projects bring some significant challenges in terms of partnership management and end-user engagement.

3 Objectives

The objectives of EURAKNOS WP3 were to:

- define the best ways to collect, store and share information, knowledge and data based on the qualitative and quantitative analysis carried out in WP2
- identify recommendations for making outputs targeted to specific agriculture and forestry sectors and/or European regions
- design a standardized but flexible HIKR architecture based on the best ways identified to disseminate, communicate and provide practical information to the end-user
- define the architecture of a standardized higher impact KR to maximize the impact of a KR based on key elements such as a successful multi-actor approach and innovation from the grass root level

Based on the outcome of Task 2.4, Task 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, Task 3.3, will select the main tools to involve multi-actors in TNs with focus on the end user in the different phases of the project: conceptualisation, initiation, execution and post execution of the project.

- Task 3.4 will define the best practices and methods to foster the multi-actor approach for the production of knowledge (team building, training, tools and stakeholders' engagement).
- Task 3.4 will provide assessment templates per multi-actor group (farmers, advisors, researchers, industry, academia) for identifying stakeholder needs for the type of knowledge needed to be aggregated into a common repository.

Following activities will be carried out:

- Actor WG meeting: An actor WG will be set up to identify and file recommendations for best methodologies and practices for multi actor involvement during conceptualisation, initiation, execution and post execution of TNs
- Actor WG members (ca. 10) will be selected from the KIP. The findings will be synthesized in a report, discussed and validated by all the partners involved in the work package, describing the methodologies and practices to involve multi actors in TNs .

4 Methodology

Members of the Actor WG were invited to participate in a two-day workshop in Paris on December 12 and 13. A workshop is a time-limited event in which a small group deals intensively with a specific topic. As a human resource management tool, it is about jointly developing solutions and results to a specific problem. In the Actor WG different methods were combined to get the most benefit out of the workshop.

- A. Tour de Table – Icebreaker/Overview
- B. Best Practices - Experiences from the practice
- C. World Cafe - Workshop Methodology

The members of the working group (about 10) will be selected by the KIP. The results will be summarized in a report to be discussed and validated by all partners involved in the work package, describing the methods and practices to involve multiple actors in TN.

For the planned workshop of the Actor WG, the main criteria of the participants were defined by the KIP

- The function of the participants: it was intended that this working group should be multi-stakeholder. To this end, a balanced distribution was ensured between different groups of stakeholders sought (farmers/foresters, advisers and policy makers as knowledge users and TN participants, researchers as knowledge makers).
- Geographical origin: as far as possible, an attempt was made to cover the whole of Europe to be able to take into account the geographical diversity, even if the Estonian delegation was predominant.
- Fluency in English: this is a necessary prerequisite to participating in such a working group but at the same time a major obstacle to mobilising a wide range of European farmers. The only respondents present were from Northern Europe.
- Available contacts: the list of KIP members assembled within EURAKNOS but also and above all by the contacts of the EURAKNOS partner network.

The invitation to the relevant actors for the workshop in Paris was drafted by the Taskleader and coordinated with the partners. The Euraknos partners were given to forward the invitation to possible participants that meet the above criteria.

4.1 Tour de Table

The first exercise in the workshop served to break the ice and get to know each other, as well as to give the group an overview of the diversity and wealth of experience within the group. The objectives of the Tour de Table is simple as it is primarily about getting to know each other, building trust, establishing contacts in the group and the facilitator gets information about the participants. The procedure is also very simple because each participant introduces himself in the round (professional, private). For this purpose, concrete questions should be written on a flipchart. For example: occupation, hobbies, expectations etc.. The type of questions also influences how exciting the round will be.

4.2 Best Practices

Best practice as a recipe for success for processes, projects, developments Companies try to produce results as efficiently and effectively as possible. A best practice refers to a proven approach, a practice or a method to carry out a repetitive activity or project as optimally as possible. It is a kind of pattern that is used to produce a defined result. In the truest sense of the term (translated), a best practice refers to an "outstanding practice." For this reason, best practices are considered to be recipes for success that organizations have developed over time, and which they apply in appropriate situations, projects, developments.

Basically, a best practice addresses the orientation to the best. Organizations ideally learn from their experiences and improve their processes as a result. Since this can be time-consuming depending on the task or the project, many companies try to orient themselves by benchmarking on the positive findings of an industry and to use the experiences of other companies. This leads, for example, to numerous suggestions in articles, blogs or books on how online marketing works best, when Facebook ads should be placed or how employee communication ideally works. Of course, it makes sense to look for best practice examples - both within and outside an organization. The concrete use of insights in comparable situations is a good idea, for example.

The selected best practices came from the KIP and were determined through a simplified process by the taskleaders as well as the participating partners. The plan was to use the best practices to stimulate discussion and promote integration among workshop participants. The best practices presented were identified and presented to the participants. Liason was selected because it is a European network project and has very good technical skills in describing the relevant Indian stakeholders for end-user integration and the current MAA approach. Waterbudies was selected because it is a flagship project at the national level for environmental and climate action and has worked with practitioners (family farmers) from the beginning and implemented the MAA approach at the regional level in a living lab approach and was therefore selected as a suitable best practice.

LIAISON is a Research and Innovation Action (RIA) H2020 MA project composed of a diverse team of academics and practitioners from 17 partner organisations from 15 countries. Between May 2018 and August 2021 we are working together to help unlock the potential of “working in partnership for innovation” in agriculture, forestry and rural business, by linking actors (see map), instruments and policies through networks.

Waterbudies is a regional multi-actor innovation project implemented in Lower Saxony (2018) to support family farms by co-developing a higher ambition for environmental and climate action, sharing knowledge and innovation to upscale sustainable resilience. All relevant actors concerned with water management are involved (chamber of agriculture, farmer associations, regional government, water, soil management and federate state authorities, research institutes and water supply companies) but addressing the needs of local farmers is at the core of project purpose.

4.3 World Cafe

in the last step the World Café was used to give the workshop the necessary activity. In this method, the topic to be discussed is strictly predetermined. The twelve to 50 participants are divided into small groups of no more than five, in which they discuss the topic and record their thoughts and results. After this round, all but one person moves to other groups, and the remaining person explains each of the previously developed results. After about three rounds, all results are presented to the entire group.

The participants are divided in three groups of 4-5 persons here and change each 30' from A to B to C etc

- A. MAA in the Conceptualization Phase
 - How to involve end-users in the conceptualization of a project?
 - How to get their needs translated in the idea of the project? 5' to change groups, moderators stay at the table, a rapporteur is appointed at each table
- B. MAA in the Execution Phase
 - How to make actors better work together?
 - Defining roles?
 - Local Hubs?
 - Role of a facilitator?
 - Profile of the facilitator?
- C. MAA in the post project (evaluation) Phase

- How to do the postmonitoring of a project?
- How to measure impact and the uptake of results by the end-users?
- Which actors could be involved and how to involve them?

5 Results of the working group

This chapter presents the results, based on the experience and expertise harvested from the participants at the workshop. In the first section, section 3.1, to set the scene for further reflection, the lessons learned from two MAA projects. This is followed by section 3.2 focussing on best practices to involve end-users and increase MA impact in the project from conceptualisation, execution and through to the evaluation phase.

Working Group (Actor WG)

- Sweden, Lecturer at Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (involved in Inno4grass)
- Netherlands, Consultant and trainer at Netwerk&Co
- Netherlands, Consultant and trainer at Netwerk&Co
- Belgium VLK+ EUFRAS, M Sc Agriculture Bruxelles
- Germany, Research associate at University of Kassel (involved in SynSICRIS Project)
- Germany, Chamber of Agriculture of the Federal State of Lower Saxony, Agricultural advisor for water protection, Farmer (secondary occupation)
- Germany, independant farmer
- Germany, dairy farmer and farm-owner
- Germany, Farmer
- Ireland, Research Officer at Teagasc (involved in the FAIRshare project)
- France, *Accompagnement du changement technique et humain Etudes, formations, coaching IDELE (involved in LIAISON project, WP leader of the work package dedicated to MAA)*
- France, *Chargée de mission Partenariat européen pour l'innovation, Ministère de l'Agriculture et de l'Alimentation*

5.1 Setting the scene: Lessons learnt from the other MAA projects

As an introduction to the Paris workshop and as a starting point to reflect collectively on the most effective way to engage end-users (farmers/foresters and advisors) in current and future TNs, two experts of the working group 3.4 presented the results of their respective MAA projects at two different levels, the H2020 LIAISON project at the European scale and Waterbuddies at a regional scale (Lower Saxony, Germany). This was followed by a reflection on the major challenges faced while implementing a MAA.

In the two good practice examples special attention is paid to two major aspects of the MAA; the MAA partnership structure and management of the MA consortium e.g. how all LIAISON partners agreed 'how to work together', and how to maintain engagement of end-users throughout the project. Please find key lessons learnt and recommendations for future MAAs in the Good practice examples below. These case studies highlight that good structure and management of the MAA within all WPs and tasks is crucial for an efficient implementation of collaborative processes. Moreover, a co-construction shared by all actors involved in the project on 'how to work together' facilitates a trust-based ecosystem of actors, increasing the mutual understanding between actors. This trust-based ecosystem is also perceived as a key success factor by the SCAR AKIS Strategic Working Group, in order to increase the size of the knowledge reservoir, as well as the impact on the end-users of the project (Chourot and Pascal, 2018).

Best practices to enhance a multi-actor approach throughout the projects' lifecycle.

This section presents the best practises experienced by the experts of the Working Group 3.4, involved in numerous innovative agricultural projects, including TNs, focusing on nurturing the MAA for the harvesting and co-production of knowledge. This section focusses on the best practices for involvement of end-users

engagement to increase project impact. Fostering the MAA is explored in three phases in the projects' lifecycles (see Figure 1):

- MAA in the Conceptualization Phase
- MAA in the Project implementation Phase: Initiation and Execution
- MAA in the Evaluation Phase

In the final section, the recommendations made by the workshop experts for the aggregation of knowledge into a common repository are presented.

Figure 1 The key phases in a projects' lifecycle

5.1.1 Fostering the MAA in the project conceptualisation phase

The conceptualization phase of a project occurs in the initial design activity when the scope of the project is drafted and a list of desired design features and requirements are created. In this conceptualisation phase, the partnership is formed and the project implementation strategy developed. Key in the project design is developing a strategy for the highest level of engagement of end-users to ensure uptake and exploitation of results (This is also described in detail in D3.3).

The development of the multi actor partnership can be quite challenging, especially if the different partners have multiple backgrounds, perspectives, priorities and modes of working, e.g. advisory organisations, research institutes and farmers organisations. According to the scientific literature on the topic, trust is vital when crossing professional cultural boundaries, as people are opening themselves up to vulnerability and risk (Harris and Lyon, 2013). Moreover, as relationships are built up through existing relationships, building trust through progression of projects and the use of intermediaries or guarantors is fruitful. The main requirement related to the implementation of a MA partnership (project consortium) in the conceptualization phase is to create a smart-space for trust between all actors, directly (e.g. partners of the projects consortia) and indirectly (members of an external advisory board for example) involved in the project (Chourot and Pascal, 2018; Deliverable 2.4). It is even more important to build up a sustainable environment of trust between all actors while carrying out innovative projects in agriculture because of:

- The numerous elements of uncertainty regarding the quality and reliability of the project results,
- The communication challenges related to the potential geographical and physical distance between the project stakeholders,
- The social and educational backgrounds diversity inside the project consortium,
- Last but not least, the long period of the whole transfer process of the project results.

Moreover, as far as the co-development of an initial project idea into a realistic and appropriate design is concerned, the translation of end-users needs, especially those of farmers and foresters are critical to enhance the impact of the project. This is a critical step. Apart from end-users being directly involved as consortium partners, further engagement of end-users in project implementation is essential. Key questions identified and discussed by the workshop experts to this regard were:

- A. How to involve end-users in the conceptualization phase of a project (beyond direct engagement of end-users as consortium partners)?
- B. How to get their needs translated in the project idea?

A. How to involve farmers and foresters in the conceptualization phase of a project

The initial discussion of this question resulted in the further break down in two main reflections:

- How to better understand the needs of farmers and foresters in order **to involve them better**, and
- How to **incentivise** the involvement of farmers and foresters in practice

The conclusion was that you have to take into account that different types of farmers and foresters co-exist, depending on

- Agricultural sector
- Farm size
- Demography of the region
- Region
- Self-identity
- Cooperative/ individualistic
- Social skills

For the reflection, the results on 'How to incentivise the involvement of farmers and foresters in practise' the experiences of the participants are summarized in the text box below.

Lessons learnt: Creating a smart space for trust to incentivise end-users engagement

- **Ensure** that farmers costs for not being working on the fields are compensated
- **Set up** Field days/Fairs/Study days
- **Contact** them directly, not through intermediary organisations
- **Phone** them
- **Provide** them feedback during the project's progress
- **Be direct and short** in communication with them
- **Adopt** a clear language, understandable for farmers&foresters
- **Involve** them in small peer group;
- **Launch** a Focus group at the start
- **Provide** food and drinks
- **Plan** timing with farmers
- **Send** surveys to farmers and foresters
- **Find** the issue of interest to them
- **Listen** to discussion groups
- **Demonstrate** the benefits (technical, social, regulatory etc.)
- **Use** existing networks, groups
- **Use** extension services as intermediary
- **Prefer** informal setting
- **Give** them short consultation work

The experts of the WG 3.4 indicated that it is sometimes quite challenging to involve end-users at the conceptualization phase if they are not included as consortium partners. If involving end users as consortium partners is not possible, involving end-users representative organisations and others organisations is recommended:

- Farmers organisations
- Agro-industry: feed companies, agricultural machinery, start ups as they can also implement the results
- Advisors
- Networks linked to farmers and foresters
- Educators/Trainers community
- Media/Agricultural press

The involvement of such mediators might be even more relevant to reach farmers and foresters during the dissemination process of TNs, when the innovative agricultural projects have their first results and can disseminate the outcomes among the agricultural community.

B. How to get farmers and foresters needs translated in the idea of a project

The first method to ensure embedding of farmers and foresters needs in the idea of a project is to include end-users in the project consortium. This is the key essence of the MAA. As indicated above this might not always be possible, and the following solutions are therefore recommended:

1. To send short surveys about their agricultural priorities and needs, using simple wording.
2. Value end-users time and interest by sending the results of the survey in which they have participated. There were challenges faced of involving end-users in surveys however. Lack of time,

low interest at first sight for the project, lack of trust in the initiative or in the ability of the project to deliver results which could help their daily business.

3. To overcome this challenge in several TN such as EUpig, EuroDairy, Bovine and Hennovation the key themes addressing end-users needed were defined at a higher level during project conceptualisation with support sector experts. Further definition at farm level with the involvement of end-users was carried out within the project execution phase (this is further explained in D3.1).
4. To translate end-user needs using intermediaries or mediators (also mentioned in previous section). The method of involving intermediaries was promoted by the experts of the WG 3.4 and is supported by the scientific literature (Howells, 2006).
5. In some cases, professional facilitators can also help translate and embed the farmers/ foresters needs into the idea of the project (See good practice example - Waterbuddies).

What do intermediaries do?

In particular, Howells' (2006) typology of intermediaries in innovation activities drew attention to the varied and holistic role played by intermediaries than was previously recognised. In the area of both industrial clusters and agribusiness clusters, a range of studies (for example, Bell and Giuliani, 2007; Watkins et al., 2015) have increasingly underlined the roles of intermediation, particularly in knowledge transfer. Intermediation also includes activities supporting local producers by improving vertical and horizontal coordination roles (Bolwig et al., 2011; Kilelu et al., 2017b; Poulton et al., 2010) and enabling the collective action of producers (Kilelu et al., 2017a; Poulton et al., 2010). Intermediaries are also argued to help in the upgrading of producers in terms of process and product upgrading, introducing better production methods to boost cluster performance and enhance compliance with quality standards (Iizuka, 2009; Kilelu et al., 2017b; Klerkx et al., 2012; Perez-Aleman, 2010). Lastly, intermediaries may help enhance the institutional environment, for example helping producer organisations lobby for favourable legislation (Poulton et al., 2010).

5.1.2 Fostering the MAA in the implementation phase

Once a project receives funding and the grant agreements are signed the actual project implementation starts. This phase consists of two steps, the initiation phase and execution phase. In the initiation phase the MA project consortium have to agree on how to work together to achieve the project objective. A consortium agreement is often signed to formalise this process. Working in partnership can be a challenge, especially where many different organisations involved with different objectives and organisational cultures. The examples in section 3.1 provide insight in these. Throughout the life span of the project this MA 'partnership' continuously develops and deepens.

The second step in the project implementation is the project execution. This step consist of 5 sub-steps to ensure effective end-user engagement throughout the project execution (see Figure 2). These steps are explored in more detail in D3.1 and D3.3. The work done in WG3.3 related to communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy is of particular relevance in the discussion around the MAA and end-user engagement in the project execution phase. Especially related to the TN project as their core objectives and project activities enhance uptake and use of the knowledge harvested (and co-produced) from, with and by end-users in the project.

Based on the outcome of the working group related to T3.3 the concept of 'Pathways' for knowledge co-production, harvesting and dissemination is introduced, consisting of three complementary engineered knowledge pathways to construct a project knowledge ecosystem:

- ❖ **Pathway 1 Generate:** co-translation and and co-creation of knowledge by end-user within the network

- ❖ **Pathway 2 Multiply:** upscaling of knowledge by the network members to end-users beyond the end-users directly involved in the TN (peer to peer)
- ❖ **Pathway 3 Disperse:** outscaling of knowledge to end-users beyond the network (advisors etc. who have not been involved in the network)

This framework is helpful for a TN especially to define its end-user engagement strategy. Each pathway requires end-user engagement on a different level. Whereas Pathway 1 represents how the knowledge is co-produced within a TN, involving all active members of the consortium, all actors engaged in an advisory board, and a cohort of end-users, pathways 2 and 3 represent the production of knowledge which occurs beyond the scale of the TN. In order to achieve its three objectives (generate, multiply and disperse), each TN should ideally implement a tailor-made MAA which allows the three pathways to complement each other, and even more, to interact in close ties, so that all the knowledge co-produced in Pathway 1 is upscaled in Pathway 2 and out-scaled in Pathway 3.

Moreover, to maximise the impact of implementation of an MAA would solve the issues related to the decreasing level of trust observed (in particular for farmers and foresters) when the knowledge produced in Pathway 1 is upscaled in Pathway 2 and then outscaled in Pathway 3. Whilst Task 3.3 looks at all communication and dissemination tools which enable and optimize the uptake and use of knowledge across the three pathways, Task 3.4 seeks to identify which actors play the most significant role in each Pathway, and from one Pathway to another. Additionally, Task 3.4 looks at how to optimise actors involvement in the MAA.

Figure 2 Thematic Network project execution steps

Based on the learnings from SCAR AKIS SWG and Task 2.4, Task 3.1, Task 3.2 and Task 3.3, the choice was made to focus on three key questions during the working group session related to maximising the MAA during the project execution phase:

- A. How to make actors work more effectively together in MA projects?
- B. What are the roles of the different actors in MA project?

C. What role does facilitator play in interactive innovative agricultural projects and what is their ideal profile?

A. How to make actors work more effectively together in MA projects?

- Develop a high end-user engagement by taking into account the specific interests and profiles of actors' regarding the production of knowledge
- Respect that different actors have different agenda and availabilities
- Assign roles and workload depending on actors' appetences and abilities
- Implement a workable taskforce on MAA (not too many actors, so that communication pathways don't become unmanageable)
- Implement regular internal meetings
- Raise openly the difficult questions, discuss about the problems which may occur during the project so no one feels left out or isolated with difficulties
- Celebrate the success or progress made during the project with all partners
- Assign clear roles and responsibilities with clear expectations
- Repeat expectations when needed
- Be patient
- Be optimistic
- Be open-minded: different cultures have different social and cultural codes, European mindsets have different patterns

B. What are the roles of the different actors in MA project?

- After carrying out a thorough actors' analysis, the MA partnership should assign roles to each actor in a well balanced manner, on an equitable basis, with regards to what can be expected from them (calculation of person months, WP effort) so as to avoid dominance amongst actors
- After defining the roles of actors in the project, it is sometimes important to arbitrate and even rebalance weights and responsibilities that some dominant actors might take on at the expense of other actors: for example, within Hennovation with some industry actors tried to dominant the agenda away from the ideas of the farmers – this requires expert facilitation
- This readjustment can be done by the coordination team of the project, or in some cases by a facilitator involved in the project and who knows the actors well (example of the facilitation made in Waterbuddies)

C. What role facilitator play in interactive innovative agricultural projects and what is their ideal profile?

- The role of the facilitator should be related to that of the project manager but not similar, there is some discussion amongst the different participants with regard to how this role differs exactly. They don't use the same tools, and differ in effectiveness on certain tasks.
- A facilitator should be involved in the writing phase, but to remain independent this facilitator might best be replaced during subsequent phases of the project. Once the project begins, the facilitator starts building a trusting space to allow healthy organic interactions amongst involved partners. The facilitator will bring the right actors in at the right time. The role shifts during the project from organising to facilitating. Meeting organised by facilitators will involve more dialogue
- Potential roles of the facilitator:
 - The facilitator needs to be a polymath, empathetic
 - The facilitator needs to have empathy, both cognitive and affective
 - The facilitator needs to be able to listen
 - The facilitator needs to be respectful of other people's opinions
 - The facilitator needs to be sensitive to the needs of the group
 - The facilitator should follow and enhance the energy of the group
- **Characteristics of a good facilitator**
 - *Organisational skills*

The facilitator needs to have excellent organisational skills.

The facilitator organises different meetings than a project manager, these meetings will be more focused on creating a constructive dialogue between all actors

- The facilitator needs to give responsibility to the group and remain impartial
- The facilitator needs to be able withstand frustration
- The facilitator needs to have self-confidence
- The facilitator should not be very visible

○ *Connecting skills*

The facilitator needs to be able to connect people

The facilitator needs to know that he/she needs to detect the key actors early on

The facilitator needs skills to understand the languages of the different actors involved

The facilitator needs to meet people F2F and meet them when there is a problem

○ *Open-mindedness*

The facilitator needs to be open-minded

The facilitator needs to be creative

The facilitator needs to be flexible and adaptive

The results collected during the consultation of experts of WG 3.4 show that the involvement of facilitators in innovative agricultural projects is crucial to the success of MAA. The role and profile of a facilitator for the mediation, moderation, and facilitation of innovative agricultural projects were intensively discussed and the debate resulted in the production of a facilitator visit card. The experts emphasised that more than just having organisational skills, facilitators must display high networking skills, and be flexible and open-minded in order to succeed in facilitating innovation networks, such as TNs. Facilitators must be able to understand the complexity of MA partnerships, and support the co-production of knowledge by adopting a positive attitude, setting a smart space for trust between all actors engaged in the project, and by triggering interactions along the three pathways presented earlier which apply during the execution phase of TNs.

5.1.3 Fostering the MAA in the post-execution phase.

The post execution or evaluation phase represents assessment of the project after its completion, analysing the actual achievements against the projected aims in terms of time, cost and quality specifications. The evaluation of uptake and use of new knowledge is methodologically challenging. Many current tools and indicators used are limited and only measure participation and engagement in project activities, and crucially not whether or not end-users adopted or adapted the new knowledge. Multiple elements contribute to the acquisition of knowledge and process of learning by end-users. The decision making by the end-users on whether or not to use the new knowledge is complex and context specific. Also as increasingly shown in the literature on evaluation of agricultural projects, any single agricultural project or program is necessarily part of a highly complex, interrelated system (Casley D.J. and Kumar, K., 1987). To deliver utility and value, evaluation in the agricultural sector must take into account contextually sensitive issues. This means that in addition to the adoption of the more generic evaluation approaches of the social sciences (including anthropology and economics), evaluation practice applied to agricultural research and development has also required the adaptation and development of more closely-tailored options and tools to meet its peculiar needs (Horton, D. et al., 1993).

The key questions related to the evaluation of MA projects discussed during the third working group session were:

- A. How to do MA project evaluation effectively?
- B. How to measure impact and the uptake of results by the end-users?
- C. Which actors could be involved and how to involve them?

A. How to do MA project evaluation effectively

- The AGRISPIN TN used a **list of ‘side-effects’**: a multi-partner contribution in order to perform a self-evaluation and also **set up a mid-term evaluation** in order to improve the effects (efficiency) of the project before the project ends.
- Collective reflections in LIAISON aim for a critical assessment of actors’ cooperation as an MA group.
- The evaluation phase can be invested by innovative agricultural partners themselves for certain criteria, especially the measurable indicators set up for the completion of tasks, and the indicators foreseen during the proposal writing of the project.
- There is **no funding** for the evaluation phase in TNs today
- The evaluation of innovative agricultural projects such as TNs is considered to remain a challenge by most experts involved in WG 3.4
- The evaluation of a project is likely to bring some unexpected results (positive or negative unplanned results) due to unexpected events: is the actual environment of TNs (very standardized) able to accompany the flexibility required by most innovative agricultural projects?

B. How to measure impact and the uptake of results by the end-users?

- The impact, as such, of innovative agricultural projects, is complex to estimate and/or to measure.
- Evaluating the impact of a TN in terms of uptake of results is quite complex because impact is not monocausal to the project work. The uptake of results by farmers is in fact the result of many parameters, as farmers/foresters’ choices are influenced by many factors. Moreover, the necessary period of time for the project’s results uptake by end-users is usually quite long, and really starts only when the project delivers its first results. This process usually occurs at a quite advanced stage of completion of the project.
- The evaluation of impact of TNs could be performed by new TNs or innovative agricultural projects, taking into account the minimum period of time required for the uptake of results by end-users to be completed, which means that in a best case scenario, a TN in charge of the evaluation of other innovative agricultural projects should look at the projects’ impact 3-5 years after they were completed.
- The uptake of results generated by a project cannot be measured entirely and with full accuracy by the partners of a given project themselves.
- The uptake of results’ evaluation/estimation could be considered a project in its self
- However, at the workshop some concrete examples were given in order to help measuring the impact and uptake of results such as: doing a survey in a postproject phase, phoning farmers
- Moreover, some tips are known to improve the uptake of results such as: offering Open Innovation Challenges and Research-into-Action summary awards in order to engage broader participation for social, technological and silvicultural innovations like in the Incredible project.

C. Which actors could be involved and how to involve them?

- All types of agricultural actors and forestry actors could be involved in the evaluation phase
- In practice, only actors who receive money for this purpose would participate
- It is clear that fundings are mandatory in order to trigger contributions
- In practise, it is better to ask actors already experienced in MA innovative projects, and having a strong and proven expertise in agriculture
- The self-evaluation method raises the problem of impartiality
- The self-evaluation method raises also the problem of significant staff ,turn-over which occurs in many TNs
- The self-evaluation (made by TN members themselves) is however relevant so as to estimate the consumption of resources (H&R, time, cost) and to estimate other variables such as risk management.
- The self-evaluation of a finished project should help future projects designing their project’s scope: project management data could be easily accessible and shared.
- The actors to be involved in the evaluation phase should be found by using the existing networks.

The inputs collected from the discussion show that the evaluation phase of innovative agricultural projects, such as TNs, requires implementation of a tailor-made MAA so as to serve the purpose of the evaluation, require both numerous resources (human, time, cost) and strategic planning.

Fundamentally what is still missing from a TN practitioner's point of view is to perform a good evaluation of innovative agricultural projects. The following good practice textbox therefore investigates existing recommendations and guidance provided by some reference institutions, aiming to providing clearer guidance to TN practitioners.

5.2 Recommendations for the aggregation of knowledge into a common repository

In the final session in the WG3.4 workshop discussion were facilitated to explore the best practices and methods to aggregate the co-produced knowledge into a common repository. One of the core objectives of the EURAKNOS project is to design a common data system to make this Multiactor project knowledge more accessible, findable, interoperable and reusable for the agricultural innovation community in Europe. An assessment template was co-designed by consortium partners to collect feedback from the experts of WG 3.4 about the type of knowledge which they perceive the most needed per type of actor (stakeholder need) in order to carry out their activities. This first investigation explores which information /or content (for example: training tools, videos etc) is relevance to be included in a digital database for by end-users. Initially, a group of ten major actor types involved in innovative agricultural projects were selected to be investigated. The results from this assessment are presented in Table (circulated through the assessment templates) are presented in the tables below.

Table 1 Type of knowledge or information needed by each type of actor

Type of actors	Type of knowledge or information needed by each type of actor
Authorities	Legislation Partners, actors, project time, results, dependency on other projects, summary (what did we learn?) Funding
Local Administration	Legislation issues, funding, the ambitions of the project, results, summary
Public Advisor	All new tools, knowledge, legislation, marketing and communication methods, social and other medias media, content for peer-to peer learning, infrastructure, facilitation training
Farmers/foresters	All technical tools and data related to their agricultural sector, knowledge, regulatory information on their agricultural sector, economical data of their sector, indicators of sustainability of their sector at local, indicators of competitiveness, farm management toolbox
Innovation broker	Networking skills, specific competence to link the right people → training tutorials to develop these skills ?
Facilitator	Methology of different studies, what is done before?
Private Advisor	All new tools, knowledge, legislation, marketing and communication methods, social and other medias media, a car for peer-to peer learning, infrastructure, facilitation training
Technical Experts	IT skills, applied skills, different sources of knowledge, e.g. conferences → training tutorials to develop these skills ?
Retailer	Consistent supply, trust, connections between supplier and consumer, marketing skills, bargaining power, monitoring body (food safety authority), where the product comes from, how the product is produced, certification, storytelling skills
Consumer	Nutritional content, where the product comes from, the story behind, certification, quality, packaging

Table 2 Type of knowledge needed per type of actor (from low-moderate (+) to intensive (+++)
need)

Type of actor	Type of knowledge needed			
	Social	Scientific	Technical	Legal/ administrative
Authorities	++	++	++	+++
Local administration	+		+	+++
Public advisor	++	++	++	++
Farmers/foresters	++	+	+++	++
Innovation broker	+++	++	+++	+
facilitator	+++	+	+	+
Private advisor	++	++	+++	++
Technical experts	+	+++	+++	+
Retailers	++		+	+
Consumers	+	+		+

This first consultation of experts of WG 3.4 provides in particular an interesting breakdown of actors' needs into four groups of knowledge/information which are respectively linked to: social content, scientific content, technical content, and legal/administrative content. Using this breakdown of needs would possibly enable the EURAKNOS partners involved in other WPs, such as WP4, to create a digital system based on different users' experiences. The desired users' experience would somehow refer to a fine-tuned and validated categorization of needs, categorization which was only initiated in the Paris Workshop, depending on the type of actor on the one hand, the appetencie for innovative content on the other hand. Moreover, the example of the 'MA toolbox' developed in the frame of the FAIRshare project and presented by John Hyland (Teagasc) during the Paris workshop, illustrates perfectly how to collect and display in an interactive tool best practices on MAA among the TN community, see text box below.

6 Conclusions and next steps

This report focusses on the outcome of WP3 Task 3.4: HIKR Multi Actor Approach. Task 3.4 selected the main tools to involve multi-actors in TNs with a focus on end-users (on the one hand the farmers/foresters, through farmers associations, on the other hand the actors of the TN community) in the different phases in the project: conceptualisation, initiation, execution and post-execution; based on the outcomes of the Task 2.4, Task 2.5, Task 2.6; Task 3.1, Task 3.2 and Task 3.3. The Deliverable 3.4 reports on strategies to enhance the impact of the MAA and presents the project work on best practises carried out by EURAKNOS members between August 2019 and March 2020. This work has been conducted, in close collaboration with its sister Tasks 3.1 & 3.3, as effective end-user engagement is inextricably connected to communication, dissemination and exploitation of the TN project results.

The input for this report was collected through a 2-day co-creation workshop (Working Group 3.4) in Paris on 12th and 13th December 2019. The experience shared by expert participants on numerous ongoing and finished projects included diverse types, geographical scales, duration and sizes, representing the diversity of projects all over Europe. D3.4 report synthetizes all the results of the workshop in light of the European Guidelines regarding the MAA innovative project implementation (EIP AGRI, 2017).

In Chapter 2, the workshop methodology is described. Chapter 3 presents the results of each activity and Chapter 4 presents the resulting recommendations. Throughout the report, examples of good practice provided by the workshop participants that have already been implemented by some TN practitioners recently (European Commission, 2015) and which serve as good examples not only for future TNs but also for manager and participants of innovative agricultural projects interested in implementing a more effective MAA are also highlighted.

6.1 Methodology

The methodology to achieve the desired results was already defined in the application as Actor Working Meeting with a strength of about 10 people selected by the KIP. However, in conducting the workshop there was room for different methodologies to integrate from the participants, so facilitators were used, World Cafe and Tour de Table and Best Practice were applied. Thus, the workshop or Actor Working Meeting was not just a workshop, but was supplemented by presentations, again designed to accelerate stakeholder engagement. The questions and the techniques during the World Café had been agreed upon with the Consortium and the KIP, as well as the Best Practices had been jointly selected. The Actor Working Meeting with the help of the facilitators was well implemented.

6.1.1 Best Practices

The methodology to achieve the desired results was already defined in the **DoA** as an actor working meeting with a strength of about 10 people selected by the KIP. However, in the implementation of the workshop there was room for different method in which the participants should be integrated, so **facilitators** were used, world **café**, tour de table and best practice were applied. Thus, the workshop or stakeholder working meeting was not just a workshop, but was supplemented with presentations, which in turn served to accelerate stakeholder engagement. The questions and techniques during the World Café had been agreed upon with the consortium and KIP, as well as the best practices that were jointly selected. The Actor Working Meeting was well implemented with the help of the facilitators.

6.1.2 Working Group members

The aim was to get as many experts as possible from the European countries. The function of the participants: It was intended that this working group should be a multi-stakeholder group. To this end, care was taken to ensure a balanced distribution between the different groups of stakeholders (farmers/forest managers, consultants and policy makers as knowledge users and TN participants, researchers as knowledge creators). Geographical origin: an attempt was made to cover as much of Europe as possible to reflect geographical diversity, even though the Estonian delegation predominated. Command of English: this is a necessary condition for participation in such a working group, but at the same time a major obstacle to mobilizing a wide range of European farmers.

Unfortunately, the only respondents present were almost exclusively from Northern Europe, this could have many reasons.

- 1. the selection/invitation through the available Contacts, the list of KIP members, the contacts within EURAKNOS , but also and especially through the contacts of the EURAKNOS partner network could have been set up more extensively
- 2. the invitations did not reach the right participants in time or due to complications
- 3. the participants could not be motivated
- 4. the strike in France 2019-2020 strike of the French pension reform

The 13 experts integrated very well in the workshop and collaborated very well, their experience in different fields was used to achieve the goal to select the best recommendations for the implementation of an effective MAA in innovative agricultural projects. The experts came from different stakeholder groups and belonged to the two end-user groups of EURAKNOS: the TN community on the one hand and farmers, foresters and extension workers on the other hand. In addition, the skills and experience of participants ranged from independent farmers to extension agents and trainers to those who evaluate TNs as part of the evaluation conducted by government institutions and others. The respective countries, qualifications, and types of actors of the WG 3.4 experts are presented below. To comply with the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation, the names of the experts are not published:

- Hungary, Farmer and Social researcher
- Sweden, Lecturer at Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (involved in Inno4grass)
- Netherlands, Consultant and trainer at Netwerk&Co
- Netherlands, Consultant and trainer at Netwerk&Co
- Belgium VLK+ EUFRAS, M Sc Agriculture Bruxelles
- Germany, Research associate at University of Kassel (involved in SynSICRIS Project)
- Germany, Chamber of Agriculture of the Federal State of Lower Saxony, Agricultural advisor for water protection, Farmer (secondary occupation)
- Germany, independant farmer
- Germany, dairy farmer and farm-owner
- Germany, Farmer
- Ireland, Research Officer at Teagasc (involved in the FAIRshare project)
- France, Accompagnement du changement technique et humain Etudes, formations, coaching IDELE (involved in LIAISON project, WP leader of the work package dedicated to MAA)
- France, Chargée de mission Partenariat européen pour l'innovation, Ministère de l'Agriculture et de l'Alimentation

6.2 Summary of recommendations to foster the MAA

6.2.1 Fostering the MAA in the Conceptualization Phase

Enhancing partnership structure and management of the MA consortium

1. Creating a trust-based project ecosystem.

The development of the MA partnership can be quite challenging, especially if the different partners have multiple backgrounds, perspectives, priorities and modes of working, e.g. advisory organisations, research institutes and farmers organisations. Investing time and effort from right at the beginning of the project is needed to build trust, engage and create ownership of the project as a TN.

2. Establish management and collaborate decision making processes

TNs run for several years and at the beginning of a project there are many uncertainties. There are often 10+ different partner organisations involved with diverse capacities and different social and educational backgrounds. Analysis of the strength of each partner and based on their strength allocate clear led roles and responsibilities within all WPs and tasks can help in maximising the MAA within the TN project consortium. As there are so many partners involved clear processes need to be defined on how decisions are made and ensure there is inclusiveness as well as effectiveness in this process.

3. Developing a common project communication platform

With a large number and diversity of partners communication challenges exist related to the potential geographical and physical distance between the TN partners. Use of a shared online platform could help in overcoming these challenges.

4. Facilitator as a key partner who enables the MAA functioning of a TN.

The WG experts as well as previous work in WP 2 indicated that the support of a facilitator can help in the enhancement of a MA where all partners are engaged and have ownership over the co-creation of the process and outcomes. During the project design dedicated budget, human and time resource need to be included to facilitate, monitor and reflect on the functioning of the multi actor consortium. This facilitator should on the one hand be part of the project and on the other hand be slightly disengaged, for example should not be the project manager. The person who performs this role on consortium level will vary within a TN based on the capacity of the partners.

TN project design to maximise end-user engagement

5. Involvement of end-users in all stages of the project implementation.

Apart from end-users being directly involved as consortium partners, to enhance a MAA further engagement of end-users in project implementation is essential. The identification of the end-users need to be involved in each stage of the project and should ideally be conducted before the project starts.

6. Translation of end-users needs in the project design is a two-step process

The first step to ensure embedding of farmers and foresters needs in the idea and design of a project is to include end-users in the project consortium. During this conceptualisation phase the higher level the key themes addressing end-users needs need to be defined. Potentially a survey to understand the needs and drivers of the farmers in the region can be conducted.

Further definition of the needs at farm level and within the value chain with the involvement of end-users need to be carried out within the project execution phase. WG experts indicated that these specific needs differ, depending on four factors, namely: technical and economic geographical, cultural and political, and social factors. This is further explained in D3.1.

7. Development of an end-user engagement strategy

The core objectives and project activities of a TN is to enhance uptake and use of the knowledge harvested (and co-produced) from, with and by end-users in the project. Hence a project end user engagement strategy needs to be designed in the project conceptualisation phase. Based on the outcome of the working group related to T3.3 the concept of 'Pathways' for knowledge co-production, harvesting and dissemination is introduced, consisting of three complementary engineered knowledge pathways to construct a project knowledge ecosystem:

❖ **Pathway 1 Generate:** co-translation and co-creation of knowledge by end-user within the network

❖ **Pathway 2 Multiply:** upscaling of knowledge by the network members to end-users beyond the end-users directly involved in the thematic network (peer to peer)

❖ **Pathway 3 Disperse:** outscaling of knowledge to end-users beyond the network (advisors etc. who have not been involved in the network)

Each pathway requires end-user engagement on a different level. Whereas Pathway 1 represents how the knowledge is co-produced within a thematic network, involving all active members of the consortium, all actors engaged in an advisory board, and a cohort of end-users, pathways 2 and 3 represent the production of knowledge which occurs beyond the scale of the TN. In order to achieve its three objectives (generate, multiply and disperse), each TN should ideally implement a tailor-made MAA which allows the three pathways to complement each other, and even more, to interact in close ties, so that all the knowledge co-produced in Pathway 1 is upscaled in Pathway 2 and out-scaled in Pathway 3. This is further explained in D3.3.

6.2.2 Fostering the MAA in the Implementation: Initiation and Execution Phase

Effective collaboration in a MA project consortium

8. Co-design of the 'rules of engagement'

All TN project partners should co-design and agree the rules for communication and collaboration. This should be done through a joint workshop at the beginning of project implementation.

9. Regular reflection on the functioning of the MAA during the life span of the project

Throughout the life span of the project this MA 'partnership' continuously develops and deepens and mobilising the multi actor approach is an iterative process which needs to be evaluated, reflected on, responded to and adjusted accordingly throughout the course of the TN. Regular reflection sessions for example at each consortium meeting making sure there is time to share and come up with an action plan to address problems and implement solutions as a matter of priority. It might also help to set up a critical assessment of cooperation and co-ownership as a MA partner and review the assessment at each consortium meeting.

Project execution

10 Involvement of end-users in all steps of project execution from needs identification to exploitation.

In figure 2 the 5 steps in the project execution are explained to ensure effective end-user engagement. These were discussed in more detail in WG3.1 and WG3.3 and the details of the outcome of these working groups can be found in D3.1 and D3.3.

11 Facilitator to enhance end-user engagement during project execution.

The results collected during the consultation of experts of WG 3.4 show that the involvement of facilitators in innovative agricultural projects is crucial to successful end-user engagement. They identified a facilitators have a variety of tasks from actual facilitation to linking and networking,

mediation, capacity building, to management and documentation'. This facilitator starts building a trusting space to allow healthy organic interactions amongst involved partners. should build trust The role and profile of a facilitator for the mediation, moderation, and facilitation of innovative agricultural projects were intensively discussed and the debate resulted in the production of a facilitator visit card. The experts emphasised that facilitators need to be flexible and open-minded in order to succeed in facilitating innovation networks, such as TNs. Facilitators must be able to understand the complexity of MA partnerships, and support the co-production of knowledge by adopting a positive attitude, setting a smart space for trust between all actors engaged in the project, and by triggering interactions along the three pathways presented earlier which apply during the execution phase of TNs. This, however, requires different capacities of partners and in some cases there is insufficient capacity to effectively facilitate this type of knowledge management process

6.2.3 Fostering the MAA in the Evaluation Phase.

12 *The evaluation of impact is complex and difficult to directly attribute outcomes*

The evaluation of uptake and use of new knowledge is methodologically challenging. Many current tools and indicators used are limited and only measure participation and engagement in project activities, and crucially not whether or not end-users adopted or adapted the new knowledge. Multiple elements contribute to the acquisition of knowledge and process of learning by end-users. The decision making by the end-users on whether or not to use the new knowledge is complex and context specific. Attribution of impact is not mono-causal to the project work. Moreover, the necessary period of time for the project's results uptake by end-users is usually quite long, and really starts only when the project delivers its first results. The inputs collected from the discussion show that the evaluation phase of innovative agricultural projects, such as TNs, require both numerous resources (human, time, cost) and strategic planning.

13 *New approaches and metrics are needed to evaluate and measure the difficult to quantify results.*

Evaluation approaches need to integrate different objectives, methods and priorities to sufficiently capture the effectiveness and outcomes of MA projects.

14 *End-users involvement essential to capture more complex and ongoing impact from TNs.*

An interactive and integrated approach where end-users and other innovation actors are engaged early in the design is needed to support learning processes and capture more complex and ongoing effects from TN and other MA projects. *Steering Group of Practitioner or representative from the field from the conceptual phase to evaluation)*

6.3 Next steps

6.3.1 Development of the TN guidelines

All the recommendations of the different working groups, including the ones summarized in the previous paragraph, will be collated into the HIKR TN technical guidelines T3.5 and D3.5. These guidelines will also include the results of D2.5 and D5.4. The recommendations from deliverable reports D3.1 to D3.4 will be combined into one document for a harmonized approach. Based on the discussion in WG3.4 what is evident is that at the heart of a TN is the MAA and this needs to be mainstreamed throughout the manual. This should not be seen as a separate element but integral part of all sections in these guidelines from the very start of the development of a TN project consortium to the dissemination and exploitation of the result. As also indicated in D3.3 we have to go beyond the functional WP task structure and develop an effective and usable content structure for the guidelines. And this structure needs to allow us to include all the work

done in the working groups, on the TN visioning and the TN recommendations coming out of WP 2 Budapest meeting, and pull all of these together in a coherent document with a consistent narrative/story, see Figure 3.

Figure 3 Visual of the chapter outline of the TN guidelines

6.3.2 EURAKNOS workshop 2

A 2-day workshop is planned in T3.5 to validate the recommendations developed by the working groups in T3.1 to T3.4 and engage TN coordinators and end-users (through the KIP & SIB) in the co-design of the TN guidelines. Unfortunately, due to the Covid-19 outbreak this workshop will not happen face to face and all sessions will be conducted online. In this workshop the results of the WG3.4 will be shared and discussed.

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8 ANNEX

8.1 Best Practice Waterbuddies

Good practice example: Waterbuddies

Waterbuddies is a regional multi-actor innovation project implemented in Lower Saxony (2018) to support family farms by co-developing a higher ambition for environmental and climate action, sharing knowledge and innovation to upscale sustainable resilience. All relevant actors concerned with water management are involved (chamber of agriculture, farmer associations, regional government, water, soil management and federate state authorities, research institutes and water supply companies) but addressing the **needs of local farmers is at the core of project purpose.**

Project initialisation

- 💧 Identify and analyse your key stakeholders before the project starts.
- 💧 Survey to understand the needs and drivers of the farmers in the region. This will not only create ownership by the farmer involved which will mean they are better engaged throughout the life of the project, it will also mean the outcomes of your project will be more widely applicable, potentially creating higher dissemination impact.
- 💧 Evaluating the aims, interests and motives of all your actors and understanding their radius of action and reach to understand and maximise the impact their involvement can have.

During the project

- 💧 Set up a work task force, known in Waterbuddies as the living lab, composed of regional actors with complementary backgrounds and skills.
- 💧 Utilise a strong facilitator who can build trust, stimulate the interactions between actors, embedding a respectful culture of empathetic exchange so that all actors can share their different ideas, interests and drivers, and contribute equally to the process where they want to.

8.2 Best Practice Liaison

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Good practice example: The implementation of a MAA in the LIAISON project

LIAISON

LIAISON is a Research and Innovation Action (RIA) H2020 MA project composed of a diverse team of academics and practitioners from 17 partner organisations from 15 countries. Between May 2018 and August 2021 we are working together to help unlock the potential of “working in partnership for innovation” in agriculture, forestry and rural business, by linking actors (see map), instruments and policies through networks.

KEY MAA RECOMMENDATIONS FROM LIAISON

During project initialisation

Allocate dedicated budget, human and time resource to facilitate, monitor and reflect on the multi actor approach. Identify facilitators who can help you develop and deliver a truly multi actor approach where all actors are engaged and have ownership over the co-creation of the process and outcomes.

At the beginning of your project

Design and facilitate a workshop right at the beginning of the project to build trust, engage and co-create your MAA approach. This will ensure all partners take ownership and responsibility for delivering the approach throughout the course of the project.

All actors and partner in your project should co-design and agree the rules for communication and collaboration.

Set up a critical assessment of actors cooperation as a multi actor partner and review the assessment at each consortium meeting.

Throughout your project

LIAISON recognise mobilising the multi actor approach is an iterative process which needs to be evaluated, reflected upon, responded to and adjusted accordingly through out the course of the thematic network.

Allocate clear led roles and responsibilities for the MAA approach within all WPs and tasks.

Run an MAA reflection session at every consortium meeting and make sure there is time to share and come up with an action plan to address problems and implement solutions as a matter of priority.

Between consortium meetings create a mechanism to share MAA challenges you maybe facing so that other partners can learn from these and share potential solutions.

At the end of your project

Reflect and evaluate your MAA approach. Identify lessons learnt and share with the EURAKNOS community.

8.3 Best Practice Hennovation

Good practice example: The Hennovation Innovation networks

In the case of Hennovation, project partners concluded that successful multi-actor, practice-led innovation networks depend upon the following key factors: active participation from relevant actors, professional facilitation, moderate resource support and access to relevant expertise. These key success factors should be mobilised right from the conceptualization phase of innovative agricultural projects. Therefore, Hennovation partners encourage government, industry and other organisations to work collaboratively to realise the potential of a practice-led approach, by focusing on the critical role of the professional facilitator. For more information see <http://hennovation.eu/results/index.html>

8.4 Best Practice the Fairshare project

Good practice example: The FAIRshare project, multi -actor toolbox

The FAIRshare Multi-actor toolbox presents the wide range of stakeholder/actor engagement methods and tools available, each with their own (scenario-dependent) advantages. <https://fairshare-pnf.eu/tool-details/5e2b18d850aeb3490a24f374>

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8.5 Best practice Evaluating interactive innovation processes: towards a developmental-oriented analytical framework

Good practice example: Evaluating interactive innovation processes: towards a developmental-oriented analytical framework

(Cristiano and Proietti, 2018)

“The novelty and complexity of interactive innovation and multi-actor approaches in European innovation policies asks for a comprehensive framework to analyse co-innovation processes and, particularly, the interactive processes performed by the operational groups (OGs). This paper is aimed at raising the discussion on frameworks and practices to analyse and support of innovation processes of OGs in rural development policy. The analysis highlights an increasing interest of the current evaluation and research practices on interactive innovation processes, collaborative learning and capacity development both at individual, collective and systems levels. Particularly, transformative-oriented frameworks have been developed in view of supporting capacity development in innovation systems. Supported by previous studies, the paper moves towards a proposal for a developmental-oriented analysis (DOA) framework which is inspired by reflexive and developmental approaches draw up in recent research as well as in evaluative experiences of multi-actor projects. The DOA framework intends to support the design of evaluation strategies aiming at assessing OGs performances and innovation processes at local level. As well, the DOA could be a reference for policy/programme design aiming at promoting the development of innovative capacities and systems in agriculture.”

Through thorough analysis of the literature this paper proposes a developmental-oriented analysis of multi-actor innovations, highlighting evaluative practices and meaningful insights applied to multi-actor research and innovation projects to expand those proposed by Lamprinopolou (2014):

- Developmental-oriented analytical (DOA) framework assesses OGs performances and their contribution to major long-term goals of rural policy.
- Combine the integrated analytical framework with participatory, capacity development and reflexive approaches.
- Support critical thinking in multi-actor organizations, through collective learning processes and capacity development paths, both at the partnership and system level (e.g. OGs and policy makers).

The DOA framework is proposed for the design of evaluation strategies aiming at assessing OGs performances and innovation processes at local level. Furthermore, the DOA framework has been recommended as a reference for policy and programme design aimed at practice led innovation. The key tenet of a DOA approach is the continuous involvement of end-users and institutions in research and innovation development, which allows iterative improvements in processes and co-learning. It is recommended that the DOA approach should be applied at the very beginning and during the entire implementation of the innovation process. For full details, please go to http://ifsa.boku.ac.at/cms/fileadmin/Proceeding2018/Theme3_Cristiano.pdf

8.6 Paris Workshop Agenda

Activity & time	Description	Facilitator
Welcome and introduction 5'	Welcome participants and explain shortly the objective of the workshop, agenda	Elodie Pascal (GLZ)
Tour de Table 5'	Every participant presents him/her self	Elodie Pascal
Presentation on MAA 10'	First results of LIAISON project	Christele Couzy (IDELE)
Presentation on a national MAA project 10'	Experiences of Waterbuddies	Mathias Paech (GLZ)
The MAA in the short, medium and long term of TNs 10'	Presentation of the D2.4 results as basis for the discussion , examples of best practices and methodologies, Intro to questions of the workshop	Elodie Pascal (GLZ)
Session 1 Guidelines for the MAA in thematic networks 1h35'	The participants are divided in three groups of 4-5 persons here and change each 30' from A to B to C etc	
A. MAA in the Conceptualization Phase 35'	How to involve end-users in the conceptualization of a project? How to get their needs translated in the idea of the project? 5' to change groups, moderators stay at the table, a rapporteur is appointed at each table	Sylvia BursSENS (UGent)
B. MAA in the Execution Phase 35'	How to make actors better work together? Defining roles? Local Hubs? Role of a facilitator? Profile of the facilitator?	Elodie Pascal (GLZ)
C. MAA in the post project (evaluation) Phase 35'	How to do the postmonitoring of a project? How to measure impact and the uptake of results by the end-users? Which actors could be involved and how to involve them?	Franz Janssen-Minssen (GLZ)
Session 2 1h 10' intro and 50' work	Each group to work on the type of knowledge needed per type of actor in an open source knowledge repository for agriculture and forestry innovation A template has been provided by Elodie	Elodie Pascal (GLZ)
Reporting in plenary		Maxime Marois WP3 lead (Idèle)

8.7 Invitation Working Group in Paris

Working Group in Paris

11th December to 13th December 2019

Practical information to the guest members

About the place

You are expected as guest members at FIAP (International accommodation and congress center) in Paris from Wednesday 11th December 2019 at 7.00 pm (local time) to Friday 13th December 2019 at 2.00 pm (after lunch time).

A single room is booked for you at FIAP for 2 nights (11th and 12th of December).

The FIAP address is

30 rue Cabanis

75014 PARIS – FRANCE

Phone number: +33(0)1 43 13 17 00

To find out more information, you can visit the website of the seminar place:

<https://french.fiapparis-network.fr/welcome.html>

***One place for meetings and accommodation,
for more efficiency and more interaction between people!***

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How to join us ?

About the seminar location: https://french.fiapparis-network.fr/en_contact-us.html

Practical information to get there:

- 1 hour by train or by taxi from Roissy Charles de Gaulle airport
- 40 minutes by train or by bus – 30 minutes by taxi from Orly airport
- 20 minutes by train from North Station

From Paris city center, you can access to FIAP:

- By metro, line 6: stop at the station "Glacière": walk about 7 minutes to the FIAP
- By bus, line 21, stop at the station "Port Royal – Berthollet" walk about 15 minutes to the FIAP
- By taxi

About the guest members' agenda

As guest member, you are expected from 11th of december (afternoon/ 2pm) to 13th of December (afternoon / 4pm).

11th December	
Evening	Arrival
	dinner at FIAP
1st NIGHT AT FIAP	
12th December	
Introduction plenary session	Presentation of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the Euraknos project - the seminar objectives
Session 1	Presentation of the Working Groups objectives and outputs Time to know each other
LUNCH TIME AT FIAP	
Session 2	Co design of 2-3 solutions
DINNER IN A PARISIAN RESTAURANT	
2nd NIGHT AT FIAP	
13th December	
Session 3	Market place: interaction between the Working Groups
	Improvement of solutions and prioritisation of solutions
LUNCH TIME AT FIAP	

Contacts useful

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We are waiting for you with all your positive energy and all your good ideas to share.

The organisation team of these working groups
for the Euraknos project

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